

Vital Force – A Vitality in Modern Epoch

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ABSTRACT

Vital force is energy or a spirit like force which animates the human body in a harmonious manner. It is dynamic in nature .It can be deranged when some external influence attacks the material body and vital force goes in diseased conditions .A homoeopathic medicine will be administered to cure the human body. This vital force is related to modern concepts of torque, spin rotation, quantum field, gyroscope to ensure the presence of vital force in the body which helps to regulate the body

KEYWORDS: Vital force, dynamic, homoeopathy, modern concept

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INTRODUCTION

The term vital force explain the existence of an animating invisible energy in the universe, whereas vital principle is a special kind of power possessed by the material body [1]. According to Dr. Hahnemann, the term "vital force" introduced first time in the 5th edition of organon of medicine and it is replaced by the term "vital principle" in the 6th edition of organon[2] Because of the Vital force material body can survive, grow, reproduce, without which the anatomical body cannot perform any function and cannot protect itself from decays. It is a spirit like dynamic. It is a type of energy with which life is preserved. This energy is present in each & every part of the body. It is the basic factor responsible for keeping the body in an animated state during health & disease. [3] It cannot be seen with the naked eyes its function in a harmonious manner says that it is in state of health. So many controversies against this concept that it is nothing. But recently so many work is done to check its viability in the body and how body is functioning in a harmonious way in healthy state. In the recent studies concludes that some energy is there in the body but the techniques to calculate this will be lacking .Before 200 yrs back master Hahnemann clearly said that it is the energy by which body perform its physiological functioning.

Vital forces –Quantum theory:-

Milgrom2006: The previously informed quantum theory of notions and entanglement attempt the model of therapeutic

process. Later on weak quantum theory (WQT) and patient – practitioner –remedy (PPR) are develop a mathematically model based on homoeopathy. The quantum field theory (QFT) is used to broaden the scope of PPR. In this Patient-practitioner and remedy are interacting like quantum like field in which patient and practitioner epressed in terms of quantum matter field and remedies and disease were considered as quantum interaction field . The quantum field was related to vital force. So vital force can create or break quantum field .if it breaks, the disease were develop then homoeopathy remedies was administered which create the broken quantum field again. The process go on. The practice and forces of quantum matter and force field are visualized by the spacetime feynmann diagram so if in homoeopathy curative remedy restore the broken symmetry. It can be represented as feynmann –like diagrams. It concludes that there is a similarity between the homoeopathy and quantum theory which is useful for modeling the homoeopathy process.⁴

Therapeutic process leads to journey of cure:-

Milgrom Feb 2012: The quantum theory used to describe Homoeopathic thereapeutic process in terms of PPR and concept of Vital Force. With this two approaches combining with the semiotic geometry it leads to journey of cure. The semiotic geometry approaches gives the patient perspective and physician perspective from which we know the disease

knowledge, knowledge of patients, knowledge of remedy as mentioned in organon of medicine 6th edition (aph.3,4,5) and tells us about the entering and leaving the disease space. Through all these we evaluate the patient and a geometric figure get which leads to journey of cure combining the patient perspective and physician perspective. The semiotic geometry represents the physician and patient perspective which can be seen from outside in the physician perspective and inside in patient perspective both leads to journey of cure.⁵⁻⁷

Vital forces –Quantum Methphor:-

Milgrom 2016: The Therapeutic encounter are described based on 1. Quantum mechanical model of adaptive mutation (QMAM) and 2. Illuminated geometric pattern generated by a light source attach to spinning gyroscope. In this the PPR generated a quantum like superposition of the patient unwell and well through a therapeutic process called QMAM. The light beam of an eclipse when it covers the whole angular momentum it means it represents the less precess (Healthy state) and when the gyroscopic spin is decreasing it increases the precess (unhealthy state). This precess represents the vital force in healthy and in diseased state. When vital force is in diseased state or increases the precess the eclips of spin decreases. Some changes took place in the body after administer the remedy the circular motion of the gyroscope spin form and circulate a curative state and vital force comes in healthy state. The two new metaphor is equivalent to the semiotic theory of the journey to cure.⁹⁻¹²

Vital forces:-Concept of spin:-

They examine the concept of spin which could be used as a metaphor for understanding the operation of vital force. This concept came from nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) to investigate difference in the parameters called spin –spin relation with time to know the concept of water between homeopathically prepared (diluted and succussed) and non homeopathic prepared (diluted only) solutions. There is no difference were observed in homeopathic and non homeopathically prepared solutions. The vitalist notions which are philosophically basis on many CAM which are discredited by the current medical model. The ancient idea of vital force were amended by the modern complexity theory. So the gyroscopic metaphor here developed might be useful for the beginning to think about vital force.¹⁴

Vital forces-torque like action:-

Milgrom2006: Says that quantum macroentanglement is a mathematical model of vital force has recently been formulated. it describes the vital force in terms of gyroscope with quantised angular momentum represent vital force in a state of health in terms of wave function. The gyroscope with quantised angular momentum represent the state of health and disease in terms of vital force. vital force in terms of gyroscope represents as a barking torque(disease) decreases the angular momentum which shows precess(express symptoms) When a therapeutic remedy is administered it increases the angular momentum and decreases the precess i.e reduced symptoms expression the remedy administer accelerates the torque and gyroscope cover his angular momentum. if vital force is in diseased state it disturb the angular momentum and shows the precess and the therapeutic remedy completes the angular momentum and less the precess of vital force.¹⁵⁻¹⁸

Vital forces & gyroscopic model:

Milgrom 2004;

theory was assumed on Cartesian theory it applies double blind placebo control trials were conducted, then we get the precess of the patient & it correlates with the gyroscopic concept this paper was published to know the effects of homeopathic medicine which is considered as placebo in to days world. Homeopathy was explained by Non locality, Complementarity & entanglement in the previous researches. As per the Dr. Hahnemann vital force was well explained but cannot be seen or perceived but naked eyes so, there are so many challenges against the homeopathy by the modern medicine.

This paper was based on several metaphor study, they assumed that gyroscope was full of energy when it was moving against the object then it created there own spin (angular momentum), as per the energy they received. If some hindrance comes in between the spinning of gyroscope it reduces his speed (less angular moment) & shows the minor effects. when this concept was correlated with Homeopathy, when a person get diseased we prescribe a well suitable homeopathic remedy, according to there susceptibility which is acted on vital force of person, but if the selected potency were not correct according to the conventional laws of homeopathy it reduces the effect of energy transformed in the patients body in the form of homeopathic remedy. As said by the Milgrom they explain this process in terms of electrons (which is bounded with energy) the energy in the particles were cover there path & revolves around the atoms, as per the time in terms of energy.¹⁹⁻²⁵

Discussion:-

After studied so many philosophy the pioneers of homeopathy says that every living individual has a vital force inside his body which regulates the human body which cannot be seen but can be perceived. It is in the form of energy which is regulates the body in a systematic manner when is in healthy state but if any exciting or maintaining factors interrupt this it shows some symptoms in the form of a disease and vital force is weaker in the body because of the disease. when a homeopathically medicine is administered in the body or removal of the symptoms takes place vital force regains its health and physiological process of a human being goes in a harmonious manner.

As per studied various literature and previous researches we can assume that vital force is an energy which cannot be calculated but it is present in the body which regulates the body and covers its path in a regular motion when in healthy state we consider it in the form of pendulum, spin, rotating objects etc. if a force is applied on it will increases his speed or may be decreases according to the motion or force applied on it. it has a regular motion which is in there healthy state when some disturbance is created it may be decreases or increases its rotation which can be seen in terms of symptoms which present at physical or mental level or may be physiological or pathological which is all based on patients susceptibility. When a homeopathic well selected remedy is administered it will affect the vital force in the form of energy which is called potency in homeopathy and remedy is called force. So the vital force which shows some disease symptom or divert from his own path will recover by the help of medicine administered and intensity of symptoms reduced and gradually vital force covers its own

path in a regular manner and patients is cured. We can also say that some high technology will calculate the energy and how this whole process is going on in the body will be measured because our homeopathically medicines are diluted in nature and it is in the forms of nano particles. We can also say that homeopathy is not placebo it has medicinal effect which is highly diluted & considered in terms of small particles or energy. As per the previous studies they compared homeopathy, vital force with the new models in the physics, mathematics & modern science which takes several years to prove and it needs to be working on it. So we can say that we need to improve our technique and studies with the modern technology in new era.

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